

Choosing Plastics for Chemical Resistance

A chemical environment offers one of the most demanding tests of a plastic's durability. Add heat, and the problem is compounded. Here are new data to help you choose the best plastic for these material-killing conditions.

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SOME PLASTIC RESINS, because of their chemical structure, can be expected to dissolve in, or be softened by, certain solvents. But beyond that preliminary determination, the chemical resistance of polymers is difficult to predict by any simple means. Even establishing meaningful test parameters to determine chemical resistance is not easy because service requirements vary so much. In the study reported here, change in tensile strength caused by exposure to heat and chemicals is the criterion used as the indicator of resistance to various environments.

How Chemicals Affect Polymers

Chemical environments reduce the integrity of polymers by two mechanisms: solvent effects and degradative effects. The primary factor is solvent

action; degradation is the exception rather than the rule.

Solvent effects are principally functions of polarity and viscosity (although melting and boiling temperatures are also important). If the polarity of a solvent matches that of a primary polymer bond, the loss in mechanical properties is greatest. Thus, a close match represents an incompatible combination of polymer and solvent. Primary selection of a polymer for a given environment should be made by evaluating those materials that are farthest from a polarity match with the environment. For example, as indicated in Table 1, nylon 6/6 resists cleaning solvents such as carbon tetrachloride, and polystyrene and ethylene glycol (antifreeze solution) are incompatible.

Pure solvents generally have less effect on a polymer or composite than impure solvents or mixtures of solvents. Gasoline, for example, has a greater effect than hexane or pentane.

Water—the Universal Chemical

Most emphasis is usually placed on evaluating the chemical resistance of polymers, and too little attention is paid to the effects of water—the most abundant liquid in our environment. All polymers and composites used in engineering applications

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have at least a nominal resistance to aqueous environments; otherwise, their use as engineering materials would be precluded.

No glass-reinforced thermoplastic resin simply dissolves in water. Even on a microscopic scale, there is no chemical interaction (solution) of water molecules and the compound. Thus, the commonly encountered modes of failure for these materials—swelling, stress cracking, and wicking—must be caused by the presence of water molecules, ionic (salt) impurities, dissolved air, and bacteria.

Water transport throughout a thermoplastic part is of two types—sorption and diffusion. Sorption is the entrance of water molecules into the resin; diffusion is the distribution, by random molecular motion, throughout the resin. If the water contact is a vapor, the equilibrium water absorption is a function of the relative humidity (partial pressure of the vapor). At low partial pressures, there is a linear dependence of water absorption (and consequent dimensional change), in accordance with Henry's Law — the concentration of water within a thermoplastic equals a constant times the partial pressure.

Variances from the ideal situation (a uniform distribution of water molecules) are caused by molecular clusters of water that form at high concentrations, and by "site effects" around a molecular bond. Site effects, which occur in nylons, polyesters, polyurethanes, and polycarbonates, account for the dramatic changes in physical properties when dry, molded material is moisture-conditioned.

When a thermoplastic is immersed in water, effects of the water are more rapid than those from a vapor environment. Attainment of equilibri-

Base Resin and Glass Content (% by wt)	Initial Strength	Hydrochloric Acid, 10%	Sulfuric Acid, 10%
Polyimide (30)	13,000	F 11,300 F 11,300	F 9,900 X 9,500
Ethylene tetrafluoroethylene (ETFE) (20)	11,300	E 11,300 E 11,300	F 9,900 F 9,200
Fluorinated ethylene-propylene (20)	5,000	E 5,000 E 5,000	A 4,500 F 4,200
Polyphenylene sulfide (40)	23,200	E 22,700 E 22,500	F 20,200 F 19,300
Polyethersulfone (40)	22,700	A 21,600 A 20,400	A 20,400 F 18,200
Nylon 6/6 (50)	31,000	F 23,600 X 22,600	F 24,200 F 23,900
Polyester (40)	22,100	A 20,800 A 20,100	F 17,200 X 15,200
Polysulfone (40)	20,300	A 18,500 F 17,100	A 18,300 F 16,200
Polyarylsulfone* (0)	13,100	A 11,900 F 11,100	A 12,600 A 12,400
Poly-p-oxybenzoate† (0)	13,900	F 11,700	F 11,000
Polyamide-imide‡ (0)	27,400	A 26,300	E 26,000

Values in bold type are for samples strained in flexure (0.25%) during test.
Key to ratings:
E = Excellent: 0 to 3% loss of tensile strength.
A = Acceptable: 3 to 10% loss.
F = Fair: 10 to 25% loss.
X = Unacceptable: more than 25% loss.
D = Sample dissolved or severely tackified.
*Astrel 360 (3M) †Etkcel I-2000 (Carborundum) ‡Torlon 4203 (A.moco)

um is controlled to a greater degree by sorption. Sorption becomes a direct function of water contact, or wetting. No thermoplastic is wet-out completely by water, since the surface tension of water (72.5 dynes/cm) is too high.

Table 1—Environmental Comparator for Plastics

Dielectric Constant of Solvent*											
100	78.4	48.9	44.0	37.7	32.6	24.3	20.7	4.3	3.4	2.3	2.0
Chemical Environment											
Strong Acids	Weak Bases	Dimethyl Sulfoxide	Ethylene Glycol	Methanol	Ethanol	Acetone	Ethyl ether	Trichloroethylene	Carbon Tetrachloride	Gasoline	Heptane
Base Resin											
Polyamide-imide	Poly-p-oxybenzoate	Nylon 12	PPS ^{6,8}	Polyethersulfone	Polyarylsulfone	Polyacetal ²	FEP	ETFE ⁹	Polypropylene		
Nylon 6/6	Nylon 6	Polyester PBT		Polysulfone ^{3,7}	Phenylene oxide ⁶	Polyimide ³			Polyethylene		
		Nylon 6/12		Polycarbonate ³	Polystyrene ^{1,5}				Polyvinyl Chloride ⁹		

*The dielectric constant of a solvent is a direct measure of its ability to be polarized in an electrical field. This table shows the comparative resistance of base resins to various chemical environments at room temperature. Specific resistance tables should always be consulted, however, for individual compounds, particularly those for higher temperature service. Polymers with the most resistance to a given chemical environment are farthest from that chemical on the scale shown. (A polymer has no resistance to the chemical directly above it.) The higher in the chart (left side) a resin appears, the better its overall chemical resistance. Exceptions to these general compatibility rules (as indicated by superscripts) are: 1. organic acids. 2. sulfuric acid. 3. bases. 4. alcohol. 5. glycols. 6. oxidizing solutions. 7. automotive fluids. 8. chlorinated solvents. 9. amines.

Table 2—Chemical Resistance of High-Temperature Resins

(after seven days at room temperature)

	Tensile Strength (psi)									
	Nitric Acid, 10%	Acetic Acid, 10%	Water	Ammonium Hydroxide, 10%	Ethylene Glycol	Crude Oil	Toluene	Trichloro- ethylene	Freon TF	
X	9,500	A 11,700	F 11,600	F 10,700	E 12,900	E 12,600	F 10,700	F 10,100	A 12,500	
X	9,200	A 11,700	F 11,600	F 10,300	E 12,700	A 12,100	F 10,400	X 9,600	A 12,400	
F	9,900	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,300	F 9,800	E 11,300	E 11,300	
F	9,700	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,300	F 9,600	E 11,300	E 11,300	
A	4,800	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	
F	4,400	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	
F	20,000	E 23,000	E 23,000	E 23,200	A 22,000	E 23,200	A 21,100	F 18,100	F 20,400	
F	19,700	E 22,500	E 22,700	E 23,200	A 21,300	E 23,000	F 19,300	X 15,500	F 20,000	
F	20,000	E 22,200	E 22,700	A 20,700	E 22,700	E 22,700	F 19,300	F 19,300	A 21,600	
F	17,700	A 21,300	E 22,700	F 20,200	E 22,700	E 22,700	X 10,000	F 19,300	F 20,200	
X	20,800	F 23,600	F 24,500	F 23,300	A 28,500	A 29,800	E 30,100	E 30,100	E 30,400	
X	20,200	X 22,600	F 25,100	X 22,600	F 26,400	A 29,800	E 30,400	A 29,500	A 29,800	
F	16,800	A 20,600	F 19,200	X 15,500	A 21,200	A 20,300	F 17,700	F 19,700	F 19,000	
X	16,400	F 18,300	F 17,500	X 15,000	A 20,800	A 20,100	F 17,900	F 19,200	X 16,400	
F	17,100	A 18,900	E 19,900	F 18,100	E 20,300	A 19,500	X D	X D	A 19,300	
F	16,200	F 17,500	A 19,500	F 17,700	E 19,900	A 18,700	X D	X D	F 17,900	
E	12,800	E 12,800	E 12,800	A 12,300	E 13,100	E 13,100	F 11,500	A 12,600	E 12,700	
A	12,600	A 12,600	E 12,800	F 11,700	A 12,200	E 12,700	F 11,000	A 11,900	A 12,100	
F	10,700	F 12,000	F 11,800	X 9,000	X 10,100	F 10,700	X 10,000	F 11,700	F 11,300	
E	26,600	E 27,100	E 26,600	X 20,300	E 27,400	E 27,400	E 27,400	E 27,100	E 27,400	

Less water is absorbed in glass-reinforced nylon resins than would be expected for a simple replacement of the resin by glass fibers. Apparently, the amide groups of the nylon resin have a greater affinity for the glass-fiber sizing system than for water. Another peculiar feature of glass-reinforced nylon resin is the reduction in stress-cracking, compared to that in an unreinforced nylon. The mechanism of this stress-cracking is at present not known, but glass reinforcement apparently mitigates the effect by transferring stress along the glass fibers, rather than through the resin.

Glass-reinforced resins contain coupling agents that bond to the resin and thus exclude interaction of water molecules, improving the stability of the composite. Thus, physical properties of most glass-reinforced resins subjected to aqueous environments are maintained to a higher degree than those of the neat (unreinforced) resin.

Evaluating the Plastics

The materials tested in this study are resins and glass-reinforced composites that are usually considered suitable for service at elevated temperatures. (See "Comparing the High-Temperature Plastics," MD, Feb. 6, 1975.) These materials, with good high-temperature strength, high melt points, and generally good stability, have the qualities

that appear to point toward less susceptibility to chemical attack.

To provide a reference base for comparison, all samples (ASTM D638 tensile bars) were immersed in the liquid chemicals for seven days at room temperature. Two sets of samples were used: one unstrained, the other strained (in flexure) by 0.25%. Results of these tests—in terms of reduced tensile strength—are listed in Table 2. Also shown in the table is a letter-grade rating for each material tested. Materials that lost no more than 3% of their initial tensile strength are considered excellent; those that lost from 3 to 10% are considered acceptable; and losses between 10 and 25% are judged fair (suitable for short-term exposure such as during fabrication or other one-time operations). Those materials that lost more than 25% of initial tensile strength are considered unacceptable for contact with the environment indicated, regardless of exposure time.

Because most glass-reinforced thermoplastics are used at normal ambient temperatures, the room-temperature data for tensile-strength change usually provides a basis for evaluating chemical resistance under "normal" conditions. For most of the resins discussed here, elevated-temperature chemical resistance is more relevant. Results of tests after three days at 180 F and after one day at 300 F are tabulated in Tables 3 and 4. If an appli-

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cation requires only that the thermoplastic part be self-supporting, the data for unstrained tensile change should be consulted. The data on tensile-strength change for samples at 0.25% strain are more useful, however, for more demanding applications.

The high-temperature polymers fall into several classes insofar as hydrolysis resistance is concerned. Fluorinated polymers have the best resistance to the spectrum of materials tested. And they have by far the best resistance to aqueous chemical attack. Nylons and polyesters, on the other hand, have the poorest overall resistance and are particularly susceptible to aqueous attack. Polyimides demonstrate good overall resistance properties but are attacked by aqueous bases and, at high temperature, by aromatics. The polysulfones have excellent aqueous resistance but are subject to solvation by organic solvents, particularly aromatics. Polyphenylene sulfide demonstrates good overall resistance. Its weak points are oxidizing acids such as nitric which embrittles the material, and chlorinated solvents such as trichloroethylene and chlorobenzene, which induce stress-cracking.

For a given series of related resins, chemical resistance generally follows continuous-use temperature. A good example of this is the solvation of the polysulfones by toluene: Bisphenol sulfone dissolves at room temperature, polyether sulfone degrades at 180 F, and polyarylsulfone degrades at 300 F.

At elevated temperature in chemical environments, the hydrolysis resistance of the silane coupling agents and the glass fibers themselves become a more important component in the chemical-resistance profile. Glass fibers are susceptible to attack at room temperature by hydrofluoric acid. At temperatures above 212 F, they are attacked by strong bases. At higher temperatures, phosphoric and sulfuric acids reduce the properties of glass fibers.

In addition to the larger losses in tensile strength of strained specimens, other, more specific trends are apparent. If the chemical resistance of a material is judged excellent or acceptable when unstrained, the additional tensile strength loss for the material under strain is generally from 0 to 5%. Thus, most glass-fortified thermoplastics judged excellent or acceptable unstrained, remain excellent or acceptable strained. On the other hand, thermoplastics with marginal or unacceptable resistance generally lose an additional 5 to 15% of tensile strength when strained. For example, 30% glass-reinforced polyethersulfone has excellent resistance to ethylene glycol unstrained; the observed value of tensile strength is 22,700 psi. When the material is subjected to 0.25% strain, no additional loss is observed. The same compound is judged fair in toluene, with a tensile strength of 19,300 psi. When subjected to 0.25% strain, it loses nearly 50% more, to 10,000 psi.

Base Resin (% Glass)	Initial Strength	Hydrochloric Acid, 10%	Sulfuric Acid, 10%
Polyimide (30)	13,000	X 9,500 X 9,500	X 8,700 X 8,300
Ethylene tetrafluoro- ethylene (ETFE) (20)	11,300	E 11,300 E 11,300	F 9,300 F 9,000
Fluorinated ethylene- propylene (20)	5,000	A 4,600 A 4,500	F 4,300 F 3,800
Polyphenylene sulfide (40)	23,200	A 21,300 F 20,200	X 16,200 X 12,800
Polyethersulfone (40)	22,700	A 20,900 F 19,100	A 20,400 F 18,400
Nylon 6/6 (50)	31,000	X C X C	X C X C
Polyester (40)	22,100	X 12,800 X 12,200	X 12,400 X 11,500
Polysulfone (40)	20,300	F 18,100 F 16,200	F 17,900 F 15,400
Polyarylsulfone (0)	13,100	A 12,400 F 10,200	A 12,600 A 11,800
Poly-p-oxybenzoate (0)	13,900	F 10,700	X 8,100
Polyamide-imide (0)	27,400	F 24,400	F 24,100

Values in bold type are for samples strained in flexure (0.25%) during test.

Key to ratings:

E = Excellent: 0 to 3% loss of tensile strength.

A = Acceptable: 3 to 10% loss.

F = Fair: 10 to 25% loss.

X = Unacceptable: more than 25% loss.

C = Sample crazed or cracked.

D = Sample dissolved or severely tackified.

Base Resin (% Glass)	Initial Strength	Hydrochloric Acid, 10%	Sulfuric Acid, 10%
Polyimide (30)	13,000	X 8,300 X 4,300	X 7,500 X 6,500
Ethylene tetrafluoro- ethylene (ETFE) (20)	11,300	F 8,800 F 8,500	X 7,600 X 7,200
Fluorinated ethylene- propylene (20)	5,000	F 4,300 F 4,000	X 3,000 X 2,800
Polyphenylene sulfide (40)	23,200	X 17,200 F 18,100	X 10,200 X 9,700
Polyethersulfone (40)	22,700	X 16,100 X 14,800	X 11,600 X 6,100
Nylon 6/6 (50)	31,000	X D X D	X D X D
Polyester (40)	22,100	X C X C	X C X C
Polysulfone (40)	20,300	X 13,800 X 13,600	X 9,100 X 5,700
Polyarylsulfone (0)	13,100	A 12,200 F 9,800	A 12,300 F 11,500
Poly-p-oxybenzoate (0)	13,900	X 4,700	X 2,100
Polyamide-imide (0)	27,400	X 7,700	X 15,300

Values in bold type are for samples strained in flexure (0.25%) during test.

Key to ratings:

E = Excellent: 0 to 3% loss of tensile strength.

A = Acceptable: 3 to 10% loss.

F = Fair: 10 to 25% loss.

X = Unacceptable: more than 25% loss.

C = Sample crazed or cracked.

D = Sample dissolved or severely tackified.

Table 3—Chemical Resistance of High-Temperature Resins

(after three days at 180 F)

		Tensile Strength (psi)							
Nitric Acid, 10%	Acetic Acid, 10%	Water	Ammonium Hydroxide, 10%	Ethylene Glycol	Crude Oil	Toluene	Trichloroethylene	Freon TF	
X 8,800	X 9,100	X 9,500	F 10,000	X 9,100	A 11,700	X 6,600	X 6,800	A 11,800	
X 8,600	X 9,000	X 9,500	F 9,900	X 8,700	F 11,600	X 6,600	X 6,600	F 11,600	
F 9,400	A 10,500	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,100	A 10,400	F 9,300	F 9,000	E 11,300	
F 9,300	A 10,600	E 11,300	E 11,300	E 11,000	A 10,400	F 9,200	F 8,700	E 11,300	
X 3,600	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	F 4,500	F 4,400	F 4,000	F 3,800	E 5,000	
X 3,200	E 5,000	E 5,000	E 5,000	F 4,300	F 4,200	F 3,800	X 3,300	E 5,000	
X 15,300	E 22,500	A 21,100	E 23,000	A 20,900	A 20,900	F 19,700	X 16,000	F 19,500	
X 13,700	A 21,300	F 17,600	A 22,000	F 20,400	F 19,000	F 19,000	X 14,400	F 18,600	
F 19,300	A 21,800	A 20,400	F 20,200	E 22,700	A 21,800	F 17,300	X 16,300	A 20,900	
X 16,800	F 20,000	F 19,500	F 20,000	A 21,300	A 21,100	X C	X 14,800	F 19,100	
X C	X 16,700	X 15,500	X 13,000	X 16,700	F 25,400	A 29,800	A 28,200	F 25,700	
X C	X 15,800	X 14,900	X 12,100	X 16,100	F 26,000	A 29,100	F 27,300	F 25,100	
X 11,700	X 12,800	X 9,900	X 9,100	X C	X 15,000	X 12,200	X 7,700	X 9,300	
X 10,200	X 8,200	X 8,000	X 7,100	X C	X 12,200	X 6,600	X 5,700	X 8,600	
F 16,600	A 18,500	F 17,500	F 16,400	A 19,100	A 19,100	X D	X D	F 17,300	
X 14,600	F 16,400	F 16,600	F 16,000	F 17,300	A 18,700	X D	X D	X C	
A 12,600	A 12,100	A 12,400	A 12,300	A 12,600	E 12,700	F 10,100	F 11,000	F 11,400	
F 11,700	F 11,500	F 11,500	F 11,300	F 9,800	X 7,200	F 10,900	X 6,800	X 9,000	
F 10,600	F 11,500	X 9,900	X 7,200	X 9,600	X 9,500	X 9,500	X 9,300	F 10,600	
A 25,800	A 24,700	A 26,300	X 14,200	E 26,900	A 26,300	E 27,400	A 26,000	A 26,000	

Table 4—Chemical Resistance of High Temperature Resins

(after one day at 300 F)

		Tensile Strength (psi)							
Nitric Acid, 10%	Acetic Acid, 10%	Water	Ammonium Hydroxide, 10%	Ethylene Glycol	Crude Oil	Toluene	Trichloroethylene	Freon TF	
X 8,100	X 8,300	X 7,900	X 5,300	X 7,800	X 8,100	X 6,500	X 6,500	X 6,100	
X 7,800	X 8,200	X 7,900	X 3,800	X 7,000	X 7,900	X 6,500	X 6,200	X 5,600	
F 8,900	F 8,600	F 9,000	X 8,200	F 8,900	X 6,600	F 9,200	X 8,400	X 7,300	
F 8,600	X 7,300	F 8,600	X 7,900	X 8,000	X 6,200	F 8,700	X 8,000	X 6,800	
X 3,300	A 4,600	F 4,100	F 4,500	F 4,100	F 3,900	F 3,800	X 3,100	X 3,200	
X 2,800	F 4,300	F 4,000	F 4,300	F 3,800	X 3,400	X 3,500	X 3,000	X 2,900	
X 12,800	X 15,300	X 15,100	F 19,300	F 17,600	F 19,300	X 17,200	X 15,100	X 16,900	
X 12,500	X 13,000	X 12,300	X 15,100	X 17,200	X 16,500	X 16,700	X 13,700	X 16,000	
F 17,000	X 16,100	F 18,400	X 16,800	F 17,300	X 10,900	X D	X 16,100	X D	
X 15,000	X 13,200	X 15,900	X 15,400	X 15,400	X C	X D	X C	X D	
X D	X C	X 14,000	X 12,700	X C	F 24,500	F 27,300	F 27,300	X 22,300	
X D	X C	X 10,900	X C	X C	X 22,900	F 27,300	F 25,400	X C	
X C	X C	X C	X D	X C	X 7,700	X D	X C	X 5,500	
X C	X C	X C	X D	X C	X 5,700	X D	X C	X C	
X 13,000	X 12,600	X 14,800	X 12,000	X 14,000	X 9,100	X D	X D	X D	
X 11,000	X 11,200	X 11,600	X 8,700	X 11,600	X C	X D	X D	X D	
A 12,400	F 11,500	A 12,200	F 11,500	F 10,900	X 9,300	X 4,100	X 4,300	F 10,100	
F 11,300	F 10,700	F 11,300	F 10,600	X 8,500	X 4,600	X C	X 3,400	X 7,700	
X 10,300	X 8,200	X 8,100	X 4,700	X 9,300	X 7,900	X 7,100	X 7,900	X 9,900	
X 20,300	X 17,800	A 26,000	X D	A 26,300	X 15,600	E 27,400	F 22,200	A 26,000	